

EH DEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

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European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP4 – Technical Implementations

D4.7 Yearly Progress Report on Technical Framework

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	European Patients Forum (EPF) - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EHDEN technical framework comprises the entire set of technical constructs, i.e. applications and their interoperability, including security setup within the context of the EHDEN Project. The scope of the framework covers, as well, components for the centralised functionality such as the EHDEN portal as well as the components which are used in the local mapping of databases and tools for managing of verifying the data quality.

While Year 1 he focussed on establishing the architecture and technical foundation, year 2 focused on maturing and provide working solutions for the key components. The EHDEN portal has a better plugin structure, the database catalogue has improved usability features and now contains a plugin-database dashboards- to provide more flexibility in (summarised) database information. This will enable prospective users who want to assess the feasibility of a study concept, to retrieve all relevant information from participating databases - from metadata to data profiling information - from a single place. The enhanced API capability will also ensure that the data catalogue contributes to the FAIRification of the data sources.

The new release of Arachne is another step forward in providing a technical solution to fully support the execution of federated studies.

On the local side, the updated White Rabbit/Rabbit in a Hat tool, improves its practical usability and makes it the de-facto standard for data profiling and documenting the ETL logic. The full integration of the Data Quality Dashboard solution in the mapping process makes sure that EHDEN employs a fully transparent mechanism to monitor and manage the data quality of mapped data sources.

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1. INTRODUCTION

During the first year of the EHDEN project, the focus was on defining a single architecture in which the different applications were considered and how they fit together.

Year 2 was the start of building towards this architectural vision. The progress on the “central” components, as well as the local components is summarised below.

2. APPLICATIONS

In this section, we describe software developed or extended by members of the EHDEN Consortium during the second year of the project.

2.1. EHDEN Portal

The EHDEN Portal is the main tool through which the EHDEN network can be accessed. It is based on a content management system that allows linkage to the different underlying applications. The portal is online, accessible at <https://portal.ehden.eu/>.

During the first months of EHDEN, requirements for this platform were established in order to design an architecture capable of integrating the different tools. This architecture was projected to be capable of incorporating new tools that may emerge during the project, as well as those that were developed in the past. This requisite introduced some technical challenges, mainly related to user authentication and effortless integration of those tools. Therefore, the planned solution was based on a modular architecture with a component that follows the plugin software principles.

At the end of first year, a first version of the system was developed to fulfil these initial requirements. The platform currently links to the Database Catalogue, the EHDEN Academy, ATLAS and Arachne. The Elixir AAI (Elixir Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) was also integrated in the portal to provide an authentication schema that allows the use of a unique login in all these tools.

During the Year 2, the portal underwent various enhancements, both from a back-office perspective, as well as the users’ perspective.

- The portal was open for a restricted group of consortium members, mostly those involved in work packages that either contribute to the technical framework or will benefit from it.
- Based on user feedback, the user interface suffered several changes in order to be perceived as more user-friendly and intuitive.
- From a technical point of view, the plugin architecture, which enables the linkage to all other tools built in the EHDEN consortium, has been rebuilt, so as to display these tools in a more appealing framing for the end-user.
- Along with the previously supported plugins, a new one, the EHDEN Dashboards, was included.
- We are currently working towards including a WordPress engine in the portal architecture. This addition will support building certain web pages of the portal in a more interactive and collaborative manner.
- We expect the portal to be publicly released during Year 3 of project development and to be used by both Data Partners and SMEs that are joining the project through the various calls that happened over the last year.

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2.2. Database Catalogue

The Database Catalogue is the primary point for data discovery within EHDEN as it exposes metadata about the participating data sources. In the first year, an initial version of the Catalogue was deployed and could be accessed within the EHDEN portal. To this end, a first version of the metadata schema to be used by data sources in EHDEN was drafted and included in the Catalogue.

- During Year 2, several updates to the metadata schema were made based on feedback received from Data Partners and OHDSI collaborators. In order to avoid unnecessary replication of information, the fingerprint exposes only metadata that cannot be captured from the CDM saving valuable time and reducing the possibility of errors.
- With the inclusion of the new Dashboard Plugin, an upload feature was developed and integrated in the Database Catalogue. This feature enables the upload of an Achilles results file, that will be used for displaying both database-specific and aggregated information in the Dashboard Plugin.
- Another technical contribution was the release of a first version of an Application Programming Interface (API) that supports programmatic interactions with the Database Catalogue. The API stands as a contribution towards the FAIRification of the Database Catalogue, as it enables machines to read and write metadata exposed in the Database Catalogue.
- The user interface of the Database Catalogue has been constantly improved based on the partners' inputs, mainly with a redesign in the layout and the introduction of different filtering options. This simplifies the selection of databases of interest. Moreover, the free text search component was improved, facilitating the search for databases of interest.

Another feature that has been improved over the last year was the database comparison, where users can choose a set of databases and compare the metadata information available on the catalogue.

With the public release of the portal and catalogue, we expect over the next year to better understand the needs of both data sources and researchers that will use the Database Catalogue. As a large number of data sources are to be registered in the Database Catalogue, we will work towards further tailoring it for more specific community needs, shall they arise.

2.3. Database Dashboard

The ACHILLES tool (Automated Characterisation of Health Information at Large-scale Longitudinal Exploration System) characterises OMOP CDM databases and helps Data Custodians to gain insights into their data. This information represents summary data from a single database, which by itself does not allow the comparison with the remaining databases in the network. Therefore, consortium members designed a Data Network Dashboard tool as a web application to aggregate information from distributed OMOP CDM databases. It uses the ACHILLES results files to construct graphical dashboards and enables database comparison. The tool is built over Apache Superset, which is an open-source enterprise-ready business intelligence web application that can provide powerful and fully customisable graphical representations of data. Achilles results can be uploaded through the EHDEN Database Catalogue using the dashboard's plugin but can also be directly uploaded in the tool.

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The information available about those databases was defined in the first instance, in a hack-a-thon organised in December of 2019, held at Aveiro. During this meeting, a series of charts and dashboards were implemented containing the most relevant information about the databases, such as:

- Person: representing the number of patients per country, age distribution at first observation, year of birth distribution and normalised gender distribution;
- Observation Period: dashboard with the cumulative patient time, persons with continuous observation per month, and the start and end dates of those periods;
- Death: information about the number of death by month, and the patient age at the time of death;
- Visit: a chart to compare the number and type of visit occurrence records;
- Concepts: bubble chart which shows the number of patients and records per concept over the databases;
- Data domains: heat map visualisation of the major data domains in each database;
- General: dashboards that show the databases' types per country, the distribution of data source types, the growth of the Network including the number of databases and the number of patients in the databases over time.

This tool is fully integrated into the EHDEN Portal as well as in the Database Catalogue.

2.4. OHDSI Atlas

Atlas version 2.7.5 through 2.7.8 focused on fixing bugs related to user interface and security bugs. These fixes extend the work from version v2.7.4 to address high-impact issues and to continue to maintain required functionality.

Atlas version 2.8 has been in development and the aim is to have a beta-release of this work by the end of 2020. There are a number of big improvements with an eye towards making the platform more performant in a number of areas. In particular: the vocabulary search will allow for the configuration and use of Apache SOLR to make searching faster. There are a number of enhancements to the user interface to allow for better performance when reviewing large result sets, in particular in the characterisation module. Additionally, the system will take advantage of cohort “caching” so that once a cohort is generated, different analyses (i.e. incidence rates, characterisation, pathways) will use the cached version instead of re-generating for each iteration of an analysis.

2.5. OHDSI Arachne

Arachne version 1.16.2 was recently released. Over the past year, Arachne has been updated to support more and different database technologies. Through its full integration with ATLAS, Arachne Central accommodates custom-defined analyses in SQL and R. Arachne DataNode now also supports local analysis execution in standalone mode.

Support of OpenID and Oauth is currently under development. This will be extended to work towards Account and Authentication Management with Elixir and ISP integration on the EHDEN/OHDSI platform. Arachne efforts in Year 3 will not just focus on overall integration of EHDEN components, but also activities that are intended to familiarise people with the network study workflow on the Arachne collaboration platform and

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to conduct user requirement acquisition for new use cases of federated network analysis and study execution as defined in WP1-2-3.

2.6. OHDSI Athena and Standardised Vocabularies

Athena is now in version 1.11.0. It has a new homepage, but more importantly, considerable performance improvements have been achieved in the last year. Search logic and exact matching features have been added to optimise relevance.

In relation to the supported vocabularies that are now part of OMOP, there have been some additions this year relevant to EHDEN. Additions and extensions include

- COVID-19 vocabularies and concepts (initially released for the OHDSI study-a-thon)
- RxNORM extensions
- KDC (Korean Drug Codes)
- ATC refreshment
- NAACR, ICD-O and other oncology vocabularies
- SNOMED refactoring
- ICD10 update, CIM10 and ICD10-GM additions

Finally, some specific sets have been added to the OMOP vocabulary and/or significantly changed, like the new Tumor Modifiers and the recently consolidated Type Concept set.

The specific addition of vocabularies is a valuable additional asset for EHDEN, in particular the incorporation of COVID-19 vocabularies, the RxNORM extensions, the ATC and ICD10 update.

2.7. ETL Tooling

The OHDSI ETL tooling support the SMEs and data sources to create the transformation scripts. The main functionalities are profiling the source data (White Rabbit), creating mapping documentation (Rabbit in a Hat) and mapping source terms to the OMOP standard vocabulary (Usagi).

In Year 2, again a few new features were added to White Rabbit and Rabbit in a Hat. We released v0.10 with support for SAS files and Azure databases. A notable enhancement was the ability to add source table and field descriptions. This is especially useful when dealing with local databases in an international team. It makes it possible to display an English description next to the field name in the local language. This facilitates the discussion between the EHDEN team and source data experts. Other notable new features and fixes are listed on the Github releases page: <https://github.com/OHDSI/WhiteRabbit/releases/tag/v0.10.0>

We also initiated an analysis regarding the redevelopment of Usagi into a collaborative term mapping tooling. A focus is on the easy validation of created mappings by domain experts. This will be further worked out in the next year.

2.8. Data Quality Dashboard

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The Data Quality Dashboard¹ offers in its first release an overview of the results of a predefined set of data quality checks on a particular CDM database. The tool is the result of an OHDSI workgroup and a demo is available at <https://data.ohdsi.org/DataQualityDashboard/>. In the last year, this tool has been further refined. Above all, it has been successfully implemented in both EHDEN and the wider OHDSI community. An in-depth description of how this tool is used in the data quality framework is given in deliverable D4.2 and deliverable D4.6. The latter is currently being prepared.

2.9. Security

Security is a crucial element when dealing with health data. EHDEN endeavours to be a highly trusted partner, in particular, for Data Partners, researchers, patients and regulatory authorities when providing tools and services for them. One of the first requirements is to have a proper security and compliance policy in place. However, to establish a common security policy for a consortium project, not a legal organisation, by using open-source tools (partly) developed outside of the project by large community, is a huge challenge. While we try to follow ISO 27001 Information Security standard in the EHDEN project as much as possible, we have reached the understanding that we do not have instruments to control all aspects nor take responsibility in each step in the ecosystem we are building. Therefore, during this period, we have been trying to find a good balance between what we can/should/must control and what not. Also, we held a 2-day workshop where we played through various security incident scenarios of what could happen in the EHDEN network, discussed their impact, response actions and prevention options. This provided a valuable input for adjusting our security policy accordingly.

As a result, an updated draft version of the security policy is currently being written and we have limited its scope to the following services that EHDEN will provide to external parties:

- Tools for Data Partners to support mapping datasets to OMOP CDM,
- Host information about the datasets of Data Partners,
- A technical infrastructure for a federated network for conducting observational health data studies,
- A service desk for users of the above services.

We have defined Information Security objectives in the draft and currently collecting information from Pharmaceutical partners about their security requirements for external software to better understand the limitations of these settings. Internal discussions around the possible need for central authorisation continue. Central Elixir AAI is currently used for authentication of the users, but authorisation is managed by each tool separately.

3. CONCLUSION

While in Year 1, the focus was on defining the EHDEN architecture and foundational technical framework, Year 2 focused on deepening and maturing the core components of EHDEN and successfully positioning and integrating components that have been developed within the OHDSI community.

The progress in EHDEN has focused on making the EHDEN portal more interoperable for additional plugins, thereby improving the usability of the tool.

¹ <https://github.com/OHDSI/DataQualityDashboard>

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The database catalogue has been extended with a database dashboard allowing the systematic capture and visualisation of key (aggregate) information from partner databases. The further development of the API for the database catalogue will contribute to the FAIRification of the participating datasources.

Elixir AAI is being used for uniform authentication of users and a draft security policy has been drafted. The Data Quality Dashboard has been fully integrated in the validation of the data mapping. The local data mapping is further helped by an upgraded version of White Rabbit/Rabbit in a Hat that now also allow table and field descriptions to be added.

For Year 3 and beyond, the focus will be on strengthening the seamless integration of the different components with clear APIs and further expansion of the integrated security system. In addition, the individual components as well as the overall integration between these components will be subject to further refinement and testing on the basis of the use cases developed by WP1 through WP3. In light of sustainability of the platform created by EHDEN, we will seize any opportunity to improve the tools' interoperability and will follow progress of other standards (e.g. FHIR, openEHR, CDISC).